

A Theoretical Review of the Relationship between the Job Satisfaction Employee Performance

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Abstract:

In today's increasing competitive environment, organizations recognize the internal human element as a fundamental source of improvement. On one hand, managers are concentrating on employees' wellbeing, wants, needs, employee performance on job satisfaction. Job satisfaction has a big impact on how an employee performs his job. Both elements have an impact on job safety and employee perception of it. A satisfied employee devotes himself to work, performs orders better, and cares for others and for himself. The aim of the paper was to assess employee's job satisfaction and their work performance with use of simply survey. In order to achieve this aim.

Successful organizations know that employee satisfaction, performance and employee engagement are crucial. The study will also look at the roles of the organization and individual in employee satisfaction. Job performance, another key success factor for organizations, will also be examined. Satisfaction leads to performance and performance leads to satisfaction through number of mediating factors.

Successful organizations are those who apply periodic satisfaction and performance measurement tests to track the level of these important variables and set the corrective actions.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Job performance, Employee Behavior.

Introduction:

Many businesses fail to understand the importance of working environment for employee job satisfaction and thus face a lot of difficulties during their work. Such organizations are internally weak therefore unable to introduce innovative products into the market to outshine their competitors. Employee is an essential component in the process of achieving the mission and vision of a business.

There has been a great deal of research conducted on how organizations can become more competitive and profitable. Part of that research indicates that there are three factors that successful companies share: job satisfaction and strong performance for employees as well

as engagement with the business. Job satisfaction can come from allowing employees to be self-directed and strong relationship with fellow workers.

Satisfied employee is a happy employee and a happy employee is a successful employee. The importance of job satisfaction specially emerges to surface if had in mind the many negative consequences of job dissatisfaction such a lack of loyalty, increased absenteeism, increase number of accidents etc. Job satisfaction has significant effect on organizational measures, such as customer satisfaction and financial measures. Third, job satisfaction may serve as indicators of organizational activities. Through job satisfaction evaluation in different organizational

units, organizational unit changes that would boost performance could be made.

Literature Review:

Satisfaction level was high whereas with poorer communication ability, dissatisfaction level among employees was high. Found that for the workers who work under difficult working conditions, working condition is an important factor for job satisfaction, so workers under difficult working conditions are dissatisfied through this factor. To improve satisfaction of employees working under difficult working conditions, it is necessary for the management to improve the working conditions. It's crucial to the management in order to improve organizational overall performance to understand job satisfaction the definition of Job satisfaction is described by many authors. Job satisfaction as "any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that cause a person truthfully to say I am satisfied with my job".

The Objectives Of This Study Are:

1. To study the factors influencing job satisfaction.
2. To study the determinants of employee performance.
3. To study the relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance.

Hypothesis of This Study:

In order to achieve the study objectives there are research hypothesis:

1. H1: Job satisfaction has as significant influence on employee performance.

2. H2: Employee performance has a significant influence on job satisfaction.

3. H3: Job satisfaction has a direct influence on performance and vice versa.

Research Methodology:

The research process consists of steps necessary to effectively carry out the research. This study is descriptive in nature. The study is based on secondary data which has been taken from case studies, books, journals, newspapers and online databases.

This paper is focused mainly on employee job satisfaction and performance. The review aims to provide on understanding of issues and questions of employees of job satisfaction and performance.

Working Environment:

The working environment consists of two broader dimensions such as work and context. Work includes all the different characteristics of the job like the way job is carried out and completed, involving the tasks like task activities training, control on one's own job related activities, a sense of achievement from work, variety in tasks and the intrinsic value for a task.

Further they described the second dimension of job satisfaction known as context comprises of the physical working conditions and the social working conditions, observed that most businesses ignore the working environment within their organization resulting in an adverse effect on the performance of their employees. working environment consists of safety to employees, job security, good relations with co-workers, recognition for

good performance, motivation for performing well and participation in the decision making process of the firm.

Job Satisfaction:

Job satisfaction is one of the important factors, which affect not only the efficiency of the laborers but also such job behavior as absenteeism, accidents, etc. Job satisfaction is the result of employee perception of how well the job provides those things that are viewed important. For the success of any organization, job satisfaction has vital importance. The employees who are satisfied are the biggest assets to an organization whereas the dissatisfied employee. In fact no organization can successfully achieve its goal and mission unless and until those who constitute the organization are satisfied in their jobs. Dissatisfaction leads to frustration and frustration leads to aggression. It is believed that employees dissatisfied with their job may be militant in their attitude towards the management. Dissatisfaction is infectious and quickly spreads to other employees and is likely to affect the morale and working of other employees and image of organization. Job satisfaction/dissatisfaction is the result of various factors which are related to the present job situations. Are the biggest liabilities. Employee performance retention, productivity and generate higher profits.

Job Performance:

Job performance relates to how individuals perform in their job duties. In addition to training and natural ability (like dexterity or an inherent skill with numbers), job performance is impacted by workplace environment factors

including physically demanding tasks, employee morale, stress levels, and working extended hours. Poor conditions and high stress can lead to compromising health habits like smoking and/or poor diet, which then have increasing detrimental effects on job performance. On the other end of the spectrum, well designed work environments, low stress, and a supportive employer can greatly increase job performance. Job performance is an important part of workplace productivity and safety. An employee's job performance can be partially predicted by testing such as fitness to work and personality tests. However, actual job performance is impacted by many factors and the result of such impact may not be readily apparent until after it begins to affect performance.

Findings:

1. Employee satisfaction is directly linked to employee's performance and salaries.
2. Employee satisfaction makes good business sense and increases productivity and career enhancement.
3. The job satisfaction impact on employee performance. Second, employee performance impact on job satisfaction.
4. The job satisfaction has influence on employee productivity, absenteeism and turnover.
5. Job satisfaction affect organizational efficiencies, increase profitability and competitive advantages.

Conclusion:

Working environment has a positive impact on the Job satisfaction of employees. Bad working conditions

restrict employees to portray their capabilities and attain full potential, so it is imperative that the businesses realize the importance of good working environment. This research paper contributes towards the welfare of society as the results create awareness about the importance of good working environment for employee job satisfaction. The study impacts upon the future performance of businesses by taking working environment more seriously within their organizations to increase the motivation and commitment level of their employees. This way their work force can achieve better results.

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